

A STUDY OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE STUDENTS' LEARNING AND TEACHERS' TEACHING STYLES

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ABSTRACT

It is widely believed that understanding students' learning styles and preferences benefits both students and teachers. As students' study in a variety of ways, it is impossible to accommodate each student's learning style in the classroom. Instead, teachers can change their teaching style and adapt their teaching to the student's learning style. This research includes the concept of learning and teaching style, and classifying it; Identifying and emphasizing the importance of understanding students' learning styles. In addition to discussing that students achieve better if teachers' teaching styles match their learning styles, teachers need to have a balanced approach to their teaching styles, so that they can use different learning styles. To review the literature related to this research topic, various perspectives on learning teaching styles that are synergistic and non-synergistic with teaching styles are presented in this research.

KEYWORDS: *Teaching Skills, Learning Skills, a collaboration of teaching-learning skills.*

INTRODUCTION:

There is no doubt that students who study and teachers who teach are different in many ways. Gaining knowledge about students' learning styles can be very helpful for both teachers and students. Identifying and understanding the learning style of learners and the teaching style of teachers is necessary and important to engage learners in the active process of learning. Although both aspects are mutually coordinated, sometimes there are difficulties in establishing coordination between them. In such a situation, it is essential to study the relationship between learning and teaching styles. Various studies have been conducted regarding the coordination of learning styles and teaching styles. Naimie et al 2010; Massa and Mayer 2006; Tuan 2011. In most of the research, it has been explained that teaching style has a positive effect on students' learning ability and performance, and in some cases, there is no mutual coordination between teaching style and learning style. Sometimes inconsistency in teaching can be especially helpful for lower-level students (Peacock). The purpose of this research is to discuss these contexts.

CONCEPT OF LEARNING STYLE:

Different terms like learning style, cognitive style, sensory preference and personality are used in the process of study teaching. Some of these terms are used interchangeably, while in other cases they are distinguished. The definition of learning style relates to the process by which a learner effectively acquires a learning experience in a challenging environment. Whereas cognitive style relates to the process of giving and absorbing learning experiences based on the natural habits of individuals by finding their preferred ways. A distinction is made between learning styles and cognitive styles in knowledge and skills. Study styles are seen more in terms of the strategies that are used for studying. In this, the learning process is considered to be less stable. Cognitive styles, on the other hand, are relatively stable. Thus, learning styles, as opposed to student preferences, can be developed over time. The distinction between cognitive and learning style is not clear-cut, as some authors use cognitive style as a more general term that also includes learning teaching style.

DISTRIBUTION OF LEARNING STYLES:

Study styles are classified into three main types. Cognitive, personality and sensory. Cognitive includes analytic/global, domain-dependent/domain-independent, impulsive/reflective learning styles, Kolb's learning style model, and Ehrman and Lever's construct. Personality study styles include extroverted/introverted, random-intuitive/concrete sequential, and closed/open oriented. Sensory learning styles are divided into three sub-types: visual, tactile/kinesthetic and auditory styles etc.

VERBAL VS NON-VERBAL

Visual learners prefer to think through pictures and receive information through visual media such as diagrams and videos. Verbal learners, on the other hand, gain more information through verbal explanations, either spoken or written.

STUDY BY LISTENING

Those who study through listening get information through listening, verbal discussion and listening to others, and study through speech. This includes focusing on the pitch, and speed of sound. They benefit from reading text aloud and cannot use written information.

KINESTHETIC OR TACTILE LEARNERS:

They like to move and work with touchable objects. They enjoy regular rest and walks.

Intuitive (Random) vs. Sensing (Sequential)

Intuitive learners prefer to receive information that originates from their imagination, reflection, and internal memory. They are futuristic, non-sequential and large-scale thinkers, and derive pleasure from predicting new theories and possibilities. In contrast, sensory learners prefer information generated from the senses. They think of the present and prefer facts to theories. They like to receive guidance and instruction from teachers.

GLOBAL VERSUS ANALYTICAL

Global learners focus on a larger goal and follow their instincts for it. Guess the main idea of the text. They like short answers rather than long explanations. On the other hand, analytical learners focus on logical analysis and thinking to solve problems. They separate ideas and place more emphasis on grammatical rules.

ACTIVE VS. REFLECTIVE

Active learners enjoy doing tasks through direct action and discussing with others. Reflective learners understand and remember information better by thinking about it beforehand. Active learners prefer to work in groups, while reflective learners like to work alone or in pairs.

LEARNERS WITH AN INDIVIDUAL VERSUS GROUP PREFERENCE

Individual learners prefer to study by themselves and emphasize doing each task independently. On the other hand, students with group preference like to study and learn in groups

IMPORTANCE OF IDENTIFYING AND UNDERSTANDING LEARNING STYLES

Study styles play an important role in students' lives. When students identify their learning styles, they can integrate their learning process. This, in turn, helps make the study process easier, faster and more successful. Another benefit of identifying a student's learning style is that they can solve the problems they encounter more effectively. They succeed in facing their problems and control themselves.

Additionally, understanding study style helps students understand how to study. Hence, students become more autonomous and responsible for their learning. As a result, students' confidence will increase and teachers' control over students will decrease. At this stage, students become the centre of the learning process and establish control over their learning while the teacher acts as a guide. Another benefit of understanding learning styles is that it helps teachers plan to adapt to the learning styles of their students. Adapting to the study style of new students is especially important because they can easily become frustrated at this stage of the study. In other cases, mismatches may even be convenient because they will help students experience new ways of studying and accommodate different ways of thinking and reflect their learning styles. However, caution must be exercised in such a situation as it may also lead to the dropout of students.

In addition, three benefits of identifying study styles are suggested: academic, personal, and professional benefits. Academic benefits include increasing students' ability to study, achieving success at all academic levels, discovering how to study in an ideal way and score well in school placement tests, controlling classroom limitations, reducing frustration and stress, and increasing current learning repertoire. Personal quality includes increasing students' self-esteem and confidence, learning how to make the best of students' brains, knowing students' strengths and weaknesses, learning how to make studying more enjoyable, increasing motivation to study, and learning how to empower students. Professional qualities include gaining knowledge of professional subjects, gaining competitive advantage, being effective in team management, reducing student dropout and enhancing their acquisition potential.

COORDINATING LEARNING AND TEACHING STYLES

It is generally assumed that students are motivated to study better if their learning styles are compatible with the teaching style. As such, those who study in visual form can study better. When information is presented visually in front of learners. This approach is called the learning hypothesis or, in its more recent version, the meshing or matching hypothesis. Conversely, inconsistency can negatively affect students. A discussion based on a review of the relevant literature has been made in such a situation.

Spoon and Schell (1998) conducted a study in a public setting the purpose of this research was to compare the achievement levels of students attending a coeducational technical institution in Georgia. In this, the findings were obtained that were in coordination with the study and teaching style. 12 teachers and 189 students were included in this study. The Adult Learning Scale was used to measure the factors involved in academic teaching styles. The facts were collected from the students. Information regarding the teachers was collected by meeting them and conducting a survey. Before this research, information related to the study style of the students was obtained. Also, teachers were given a list of teaching styles. Based on this list, teachers and students were divided into congruent and incongruent groups. Statistical analysis in this regard shows that there was no significant difference between the two groups. Thus, this research failed to support the hypothesis outlined in the context of the study.

Massa and Mayer (2006) studied 52 college students in the Department of Psychology at the University of California in three experiments. The researchers created a computer-based classroom on electronics. Two different types of help screens were created to provide non-verbal and verbal learners with pictures and printed text respectively. Verbal and non-verbal learners were separated from each other using multiple measures that assessed learning preferences, cognitive styles, and spatial abilities. The aim was to find out whether visualizers learn better from integrated instructions. Those who study well with help screens that use pictures or help screens that use words study well. This showed that there was no trend towards better performance for students who were offered help screens that matched their learning style preferences. Thus, the results of providing different study methods for visual and verbal learners were not supported.

Cook (2009) studied 123 intern physicians and delivered a web-based ambulatory module. They set the following goals for this research, students with perceptual learning styles will perform better. Students with an intuitive learning style will perform well in the opposite way. Participating students were asked to complete two modules. Format of instructions. Given at the end of each module, a test was used to determine key outcomes. Comparisons were made between the two test scores. Statistical analysis of the results revealed no significant relationship between the two instruction formats.

Constantinidou and Baker (2002) studied the effect of presentation methods on the verbal learning of 52 young and older adults. An experimental method was used for this. In the collection of information, information about the study method preferences of the students was obtained and based on that, their study abilities were estimated. The Visualizer-Verbalizer Questionnaire (VVQ) was used to examine the relationship between performance in verbal free-recall on tasks that represented words via the visual modality, the auditory modality, or both. The VVQ contains many questions that require students to prioritize verbal versus visual methods. This indicated that there was no positive significant relationship between VVQ scores and free-recall level performance for different input modalities. The visual presentation was found to be better than the verbal presentation. Thus, the researchers found no significant relationship between visual and verbal presentation.

Sternberg (1999) conducted a study in which an exploratory task was conducted to determine whether study styles matched the instruction they received. A group of 324 brilliant high school students were selected for this. The selection process was conducted based on the student's performance on Sternberg Triarchic Abilities (STA). The creative, analytical and practical abilities of each student were determined through the test. Based on the test scores, the researchers selected a group of 112 students who received higher ratings for one than the other two. Based on their skill areas, the students were divided into three groups. Highly creative, highly analytical and highly practical. Another group of 87 students was divided into two other sub-groups and the remaining subjects were not included in the study. Participating students then enrolled in psychology courses at Yale University, and each subject was randomly selected to participate in a class that focused on creative, analytical, and practical instruction or memory instruction. The course was evaluated using various measures. Analysis of the facts showed that the performance of the matched subjects was compared with that of the mismatched subjects. It found that matched subjects outperformed their mismatched peers on two out of three types of assessments.

Peacock (2001) conducted a study to test the hypothesis that a mismatch between learning and teaching styles leads to learning failure and frustration. Data were collected from 46 EFL teachers and 206 EFL students at a university in Hong Kong using Reed's questionnaire, tests and interviews. It was found that teachers preferred auditory, kinesthetic and group styles and disliked individual and tactile styles while students preferred auditory and kinesthetic styles and disliked group and individual styles. Thus, inconsistencies were noted regarding auditory and group styles. Based on the interview it indicated that 70% of the students were frustrated due to a mismatch between study and teaching style. 76% said it negatively affected their studies, And 81% of teachers were satisfied with Reed's hypothesis. Finally, Peacock proposed a balanced learning style for teachers to adapt to different learning styles.

Naimie et al (2010) investigated the effect of cooperative and noncooperative learning styles on student achievement. 310 students were randomly selected from the Faculty of Foreign Languages of Azad University, Iran. Felder and Solomon's (1997) Learning Style Index (LSI) Data were collected through observations, survey questionnaires and interviews. These were defined as active/reflective, sensory/intuitive, visual/verbal, and global/sequential. Study style preferences and achievement scores of matched-study-teaching styles were compared with mismatched study-teaching styles on all four dimensions. The results of the study revealed that active, sensing, visual and global were the main learning styles of the students. To explore the effect of coordination on learning and teaching styles, students were classified into five groups on a rating scale (0-4), with 0 indicating no complete coordination and 4 indicating perfect coordination. Analysis of the results revealed that the matching of learning and teaching methods has a positive impact on student achievement.

Tuan (2011) conducted a study to identify how teachers perceive their students' learning preferences as well as the degree of discrepancy between students' and teachers' learning teaching styles. This has resulted in low performance and frustration for the students. For this purpose, 12 teachers and 168 students from eight EFL classes in Vietnam were selected as the sample. The data was collected using a questionnaire survey among students of lower secondary and intermediate classes consisting of 44 closed-ended questions. Student-teacher studies were measured through teaching style, matching classes, and observation. These results showed that Vietnamese learners were more visual learners than verbal learners, and more intuitive than sensory. was more active than sequential and reflective than global. There was also some discrepancy between the student's learning style and the teacher's teaching style. After adapting to learning styles, several teaching strategies such as Felder's

(1993) and Kolb's (1984) were applied to enhance learners' styles. The teacher's role was to guide students to a particular study style, while they had to familiarize themselves with new study styles. Although some students and teachers fail with style stretching, studies have confirmed the benefits of style stretching and matching.

From personal experience, as a student, I have always scored higher in those subjects where my study style matches the teaching style of my teacher. This consistency has helped me anticipate teacher expectations for required answers. I am an analytical student and I prefer to analyze and think in exams. So before answering the questions, I have to consider the teaching style of the teacher. However, I found, at times, that my study style and my teacher's teaching style did not mesh well. This aspect helps me to make necessary changes in my study style and to introduce and adopt more teaching styles.

CONCLUSION:

From the above discussion, it can be seen that study style plays an important role in the lives of students. When students identify their learning styles, they will be able to integrate their learning process. As a result, it will help to make the study process enjoyable, faster and more effective. Furthermore, teachers should try to adjust their teaching styles to match the learning styles of their students. However, inconsistencies in study teaching can sometimes be important especially for lower-level students as they feel frustrated at the initial stage of study but caution should be exercised. In addition, teachers should strive for a balanced teaching style in which no one teaching style is preferred but an attempt is made to accommodate multiple learning styles.

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